

A Randomized Feasibility Trial, Fidelity, and Indicative Effects of a Manualized Cognitive Training Toolkit (MCTT) on Neurocognitive Functioning of Children aged 6-11 years with ADHD

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ABSTRACT

Objectives: The study investigated the feasibility, indicative impact, and fidelity of a manualized cognitive training toolkit (MCTT) for children aged 6-11 years with medically diagnosed attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD). MCCT was compared to two available computerized cognitive training namely, PSS CogRehab and CogMed. **Method:** 32 children with ADHD without co-morbidity were randomly assigned to MCTT/PSSCogRehab/CogMed/TAU in a 1:1:1:1 ratio. Cognitive Assessment System-II, Children's Colour Trail Test 1-2, and Porteus Maze Test evaluated cognition. **Results:** 21 feasibility and 10 fidelity criteria were evaluated. Six experts determined MCTT's face and content validity. MCTT had face and content validity (SCVI=0.97). Two raters agreed on 93.45% of 10 MCTT procedural elements for fidelity. MCTT met 18 of 21 feasibility and most fidelity criteria. MCCT had significant treatment effects ranging from medium to large effect size on almost all tools. **Conclusion:** RCTs on MCTT are viable. MCTT, PSSCogRehab, and modified CogMed had comparable treatment effects on some cognitive tasks. PSSCogRehab needs Indian adaptation to reduce its difficulty level for this age group.

Keywords: ADHD, Manualized Cognitive Training Toolkit, PSS CogRehab and CogMed.

INTRODUCTION

Cognitive intervention is a set of methods for systematic and focused brain training to increase attention, working memory, problem-solving, reading, and psychosocial functioning. Focused cognitive intervention improves performance only on training tasks (Melby-Lervåg, et al., 2016). Benefits of cognitive intervention's date back over 60 years to reduce general and specific cognitive deficits in children with ADHD (Alloway & Passolunghi, 2011; Satapathy, et al., 2020). From 2000 forward, cognitive training changed significantly with computerized cognitive training (CCT) for specific cognitive domains such as visuo-spatial working memory (CogMed Working Memory Training (Klingberg, et al., 2005), which improved response inhibition and reasoning in a reduction of parent rated ADHD inattentive symptoms. Similar CCT products proliferated after 2010. CogMed has more ADHD research evidence though (Klingberg, et al., 2005; Meiran, et al., 2009) its far-transfer benefits have been negative (Au, et al., 2015), limited, and/or short-lived positive results (Chako, et al., 2014) in different cognitive areas. Other working memory products are similar.

While CCT solutions have multiplied in developed nations between 2010-2022, these products' effects either rarely examined in low-resource nations or poor children were underrepresented in the sample (Russell, Ford, & Russell, 2015). The reasons may include the high cost of the product, procurement and import issues related to foreign products, absence/limited availability of or access to computers in public hospital/schools or

homes, cost of the intervention at a private clinic, lack of awareness regarding the existence of such a product for cognitive training in children with ADHD, and no governmental effort to address ADHD specific needs. Despite recommendations of clinical practice guidelines for multimodal (pharmacological and non-pharmacological together) intervention for 6-12 years (Enns, et al., 2017), the research on manualized/computerized cognitive intervention is non-existent. In addition, multimodal treatment should be encouraged in these countries (Drechsler, et al., 2020) even for increased medication adherence and better cognitive outcomes.

Although the need for theoretically based training methods was highlighted to improve ADHD cognitive symptoms, little attempt has been made toward manualized cognitive training tools (MCTT) that are multidomain, structured and replicable, methodologically sound, and comparable to computerized tools in treatment effects. This is perhaps the first such study to develop and test the feasibility, and fidelity of a MCTT for 6-11-year-olds with ADHD based on PASS (planning, attention, simultaneous and successive processing) theory (Naglieri & Rojahn, 2004). Also, the impact assessment of MCTT as compared to CCT (PSSCogRehab & Cogmed) is novel in India and followed the trend in the feasibility literature (Abbott, 2014) and suggestion to evaluation of participant responses to intervention (Orsmond & Cohn, 2015). It also intended calibration (in terms of type of tasks, exposure duration, difficulty level, etc.) of the MCTT.

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MATERIALS AND METHODS

Participants (Figure-1): 88 ADHD-diagnosed (on medication) children were assessed for eligibility. After applying inclusion (male/female; 6-11 years; average IQ; novice to non-pharmacological/cognitive intervention, and consenting) and exclusion (co-morbidity, taking medication to treat a behavioural/psychiatric/neurological/medical condition other than ADHD) criteria, 38 children were randomly allocated to four groups. Figure-1 depicted

the CONSORT Flow Chart. Finally, 32 children were retained (MCTT = 8, PSSCogRehab= 8, and CogMed=8) and one control (Treatment as Usual-TAU=8). TAU included clinical examination, medication, and parent psychoeducation, whereas the three experimental groups additionally received designated interventions. No child's medication dose changed during the 2-week intervention. All four groups were asked to avoid any psychosocial or cognitive interventions for 3 months (till intervention completion and follow up assessments).

Figure 1: Consort Flow Diagram of Participants

Randomization: It was done via a computer and the allocation sequence was hidden. A person not involved in assessment or intervention coded each child's allocation and maintained their identifying details in a sealed envelope with superscribed code.

Double Blinding: The children were blinded to the type of intervention allocation. Second, project workers who administered assessment tools and intervention sessions were not involved in random group allocation and concealment, so were blinded to group allocation.

Bias: To reduce observer bias, the baseline, intervention, and post-intervention assessors were different for each kid. To eliminate measurement bias, the person who completed a particular child's baseline assessment did not do that child's post- or follow-up assessments or intervention. The clinical psychologists rotated doing this systematically.

Therapist Training: Three personnel who did assessment had two years of postgraduate psychology; one had research experience in neuropsychology and two were licensed clinical psychologists. Similarly, two licensed clinical psychologists (RM and JK) were trained and supervised in the delivery of MCTT, Cogmed, and PSSCogRehab.

Triangulation: While SS and RS randomly verified intervention sessions, data recording during intervention, verification of raw data sheet and checking of data entry for each child was done regularly.

TOOLS

Seguin Form Board Test (SFBT) is a performance-based IQ test for children ages 3-11 used for inclusion of IQ 85 and above (Basavarajappa, et. al., 2009). *Cognitive Assessment System- II (CAS-II)* (Naglieri & Das, 1997): Each of the four scales has two subtests (such as planned codes and connection, completing a series of matrices, visuo-spatial tasks, word series, verbal-spatial relation, expressive attention, and sentence repetition). *Children's Colour Trail Making Test-TMT* (Reitan, 1958): It's a pen-and-paper test that measures 5-16-year-olds' alternate and sustained visual attention, psychomotor speed, sequencing, inhibition-disinhibition, and cognitive flexibility. It measures focused attention and sophisticated visual scanning with a motor component in the presence of distracting stimuli. Impulsivity and executive functions were tested through *Porteus Mazes Test (PMT)* (Porteus, 1965).

Description of Interventions (Table-1)

1) Manualized Cognitive Training Toolkit (MCTT)

Description of Cognitive Tasks/Activities: Based on PASS theory, MCTT is a multidomain, structured, manually administered, sensory integration-based activity toolkit with 36 cognitive tasks spread over 9 cognitive domains: planning (P), sustained attention (A), simultaneous processing (SiP), successive processing (SuP), working

memory (WM), language skills (LS), visual-spatial processing (VSP), mind-motor coordination (MMC) (BB).

Setting: MCTT was provided at an outpatient department of a tertiary care teaching hospital. It can be administered in any setting with 1 day of training and supervision to a licensed psychologist.

Format of MCTT: MCTT is delivered individually on one-to-one basis.

Procedural Manual: MCTT has a complete procedure-based bi-lingual manual with step-by-step instructions for conducting each activity, scoring of each task, assigning child's competency level, a description of all 36 cognitive tasks and the cognitive domain each task corresponds to, etc.

Product: MCTT contains safe, non-toxic, multi-color child-friendly materials for 36 activities. Each cognitive task has a demonstration-cum practice task.

Difficulty Criteria: Difficulty level is increased according to age (6-7 years, 8-9 years, and 10-11 years), no. of attempts, time taken, creative task completion, and no. of correct responses. Details are in the MCTT manual's activity description section. The child has to complete 36 cognitive tasks, 4-5 tasks in every session. Although a total of 12 difficulty level is there for each task, a child has to complete all 36 tasks in 8 levels of difficulty.

Selecting and sequencing the activities for a Session: Each child has 8 sessions over two weeks. 90-120-minute sessions can be held. Depending on how long it takes a child to reach a certain level of competency, the length of each session can vary even within the same age group.

Flexibility: The therapist can arrange the activities (at least one activity from any 6 cognitive domains in one session) so that all 36 are completed. Since cognitive task materials are colourful and appealing, the therapist can honour the child's desire to do a selected task but without skipping any task or disrupting the sequence.

Aids: A mobile or conventional stopwatch can be used to adhere to time stimulus exposure.

Continuation & Discontinuous rules: The MCTT provides explicit principles for continuation (e.g., how to continue if a child discontinues after a few sessions but returns after a few days/weeks) and discontinuation (if a child can't perform on a particular cognitive task even after demonstration-cum-practice), etc.

Assessing Competency: Basic and advanced level of competency is scored; details are in the MCTT manual. Each child must complete basic, and if willing may complete advanced level. All study participants were basic-level completers.

Response recording and progress monitoring sheets: On a response sheet, each child's task performance is scored.

Each sheet has 9 activities to score. This page also tracks a child's competency (basic, desirable, and advanced). A progress monitoring sheet tracks all tasks accomplished in a designated session.

2) **PSSCogRehab**: It's a 67-task cognitive rehabilitation software. This study used 6 tasks each from attention, executive function, memory, visuospatial, problem solving, and communication domain on a PC or laptop. Thus, children completed all 36 tasks in 60-90 minutes per day of training, depending on type and difficulty of tasks. PSSCog Rehab offered individual task results for time, difficulty, error, pass, and consecutive passes.

3) **CogMed**: CogMed focuses on visuospatial and verbal working memory. Children were trained four trails a day for 45-60 minutes, depending on complexity. This application graphs child task performance.

Table-1 compared three cognitive intervention protocols. CogMED allows children to collect blocks to build a city after all sessions, MCTT provides verbal and PSSCogRehab provides audio feedback. Number and length of sessions in both computerized interventions were calibrated to maintain some uniformity in exposure of cognitive tasks as in MCTT.

Table 1: Intervention Protocol for MCTT, PSSCogRehab, and CogMed

Intervention Name	No. of Cognitive Tasks	Sessions*	Duration	Cognitive Domains focused	Difficulty Level	Session Frequency	Discontinuation Rule	Feedback to Participants on progress	Participants' Feedback
MCTT	36	8	12 Hours	P, SA, SiP, SuP, LS, MMC, BB, WM, VSP	1-8	8 days over two weeks	Unable to perform after 2 practice sessions	Present (Verbal by therapist)	Present
PSSCog Rehab	36	8	12 Hours	A, EF, M, V, PS, C	1-4	8 days over two weeks	Unable to perform 3 consistency level	Present (inbuilt audio feedback)	Absent
CogMed	25 blocks: 5 activities in each block	8	9-10 Hours	WM	1-9	8 days over two weeks	No provision	Present (child comes to know about progress from no. of correct or wrong responses shown in the screen)	Absent

Parents' Involvement: Parents were allowed to sit through the intervention and if they were not able to sit in few sessions they are briefed on the cognitive activities, and child's performance.

Children' Feedback: A 3-point Likert questionnaire with 5 questions for children was used to collect children's feedback.

Pretesting: Pretesting of each intervention was done on two children to understand difficulties in administration, maintaining time, children's willingness to complete the day specific session, and fatigue and boredom level of children.

Content Validity of MCTT (Figure-2): The expert panel for content validation included 4 licensed clinical psychologists, 1 neuropsychologist, and 1 child psychologist and their mean age was 30.7 years (± 3.1). The number of years of experience varied from 2-11 years. After demonstration of MCTT, experts rated 13 indices (age appropriateness of cognitive tasks/activities, gender neutrality, potentiality for cross-cultural application, relevance of displayed tasks/activities, total number of tasks, cognitive domains being evaluated, exposure duration, task specific instruction, description and detailing in the manual, use of child-safety materials, response recording and progress monitoring mechanisms, feedback provisions, and replicability) on a 3-point Likert scale (appropriate, not appropriate or not sure). Tasks were considered as "appropriate" if at least 50% of the experts agreed.

An acceptable Item (here, cognitive task)-Content Validity Index (I-CVI) (Lynn, 1986) as at least 0.78 and the Scale (here, MCTT Intervention) -Content Validity Index (S-CVI) as 0.90 (Polit, Beck & Owen, 2007) was considered appropriate. The experts rated the difficulty of contents for children aged 6-11 years, adequacy of cognitive domains, likely effectiveness of contents/tasks to reduce cognitive deficits, adequacy of content description, relevance of content delivery, total duration of MCTT, and feasibility of content delivery on a 4-point rating scale (1=not relevant and no clarity in content delivery, 2= relevant but unsure about few contents, 3= contents are relevant with adequate clarity, and 4= very relevant contents with adequate clarity). I-CVI is computed as the number of experts giving a rating 3 or 4 to the relevancy of content of tasks, divided by the total number of experts (Lawshe, 1975).

Fidelity Analysis of MCTT: In the absence of fidelity analysis guidelines for manualized cognitive interventions, we adapted sensory integration guidelines for ADHD (Parham et al., 2007). Two clinical psychologists (therapists) were trained on MCTT administration during the pretest and two senior clinical and child psychologists (SS & RS) rated the therapists on a fidelity instrument that measured process/procedural aspects of MCTT administration/delivery followed during intervention. Each rater separately rated each therapist in 2 sessions (randomly opted by the raters) for 4 children (thus 8 sessions for each therapist) on a 3-points Likert Scale

(the therapist uses this strategy: 0=Does not use; 1 = therapist somewhat uses; 2 = definitely uses) on the fidelity instrument. The therapists were blinded to the intention of the raters. Raters generated a consensus on the process elements, overall consistency and reproducibility of the procedural elements of MCTT followed by both therapists.

Feasibility Analysis of MCTT:

Feasibility was evaluated on 14 indicators based on existing guidelines (Shanyinde, Pickering, Weatherall, 2011) along with 7 other parameters suggested in literature (Stewart, et. al., 2020, Abbott, 2014; Orsmond GI, & Cohn, 2015).

RESULTS

Content validity of MCTT (Figure-2)

The I-CVI was 1.0 for five parameters (adequacy of content domains as per ADHD cognitive deficits, likely effectiveness of contents to improve cognitive functioning, adequacy of content description, relevance of content delivery total duration, feasibility of content delivery) and 0.83 for difficulty of contents for children aged 6-11 years. Thus, the SCVI for the MCTT was 0.97 establishing excellent content validity, and the panel viewed the name of the intervention appropriate, thus established its face validity. On suggestion, difficulty level of few tasks was increased for 10-11 years children.

Figure 2: Expert panel ratings of MCTT on 13 indices

Socio-demographic profile

38 children were randomly allocated to MCTT (N=10), PSSCogRehab (N=8), CogMed (N=8), and TAU (N=12). 6 children (16%) dropped out after the baseline assessment (Figure-1). Out of 32 children, 24% aged 6-7 years, 30% aged 8-9 years, and 45% were between 10-11 years. 87% were boys. While 15% of the children were diagnosed as inattentive type and 30% were hyperactivity type, 54% had impulsivity along with inattentive and hyperactivity. 15% of the children were studying in 1st class, 18% each in 2nd and 3rd class, 21% in 4th class, 18% belonged to 5th class, and 12% were in 6th class. 81% of the children were attending private schools, 87% of the children reported normal

development as recorded in medical record, and 81% children were first born.

Baseline: The mean age was 8.82 years and mean IQ was 97.5. Children in four groups did not differ significantly on age ($\chi^2=47.96$ $p < .891$), IQ ($\chi^2= 55.68$, $p < .957$) and on any assessment tool at baseline.

Feasibility Analysis (Table-2)

Randomization of 38 children was successfully done and all 32 samples in four arms were retained from baseline to 3 months follow up assessment indicating 100% intervention adherence. MCTT met 18 out of 21 criteria for feasibility analysis, thus, found to be a feasible cognitive intervention.

Table 2: Methodological analysis of feasibility parameters of MCTT, PSSCogRehab, and CogMed

Domains of Feasibility Evaluation	Methodological Criteria for feasibility trial analyzed	Findings	Evidence	Remarks
Eligibility, Recruitment & Randomization	1. What factors influenced eligibility and what proportion of those approached were eligible? And how was the enrollment?	Not fulfilling age criteria, IQ, location of residence, and comorbidity.	Assessed for eligibility (N=88) and 38 (43%) were eligible and enrolled over a period of 12 months.	Strictly following inclusion criteria resulted in slow recruitment on an average 3.1 children per month.
	2. Did eligible participants' consent?	38 (100%) consented	100% There was high conversion to consent.	Successful
	3. Was recruitment successful?	38 (100%) recruited	100% eligible sample were recruited.	
	4. Were participants successfully randomized?	Yes N=38	Experimental Arms: N=30 (MCTT-10, PSSCogRehab-8, CogMed-12) TAU as Control Group. N=8	Successfully randomized
	5. Was there any risk of contamination?	No	1)Parents, children and therapists were blinded to randomization. 2) Each session in each intervention was done in individual format	No apparent risk of contamination
Post-randomization Attrition	6. Whether participant dropped out after randomization	Attrition at this stage is defined as dropout after baseline assessment	6 children (2 from MCTT and 4 from Cogmed): Total 15.8% dropped out due to Covid-19 infection. 32 children constituted the final sample.	15.8% Drop out was in acceptable range
Data Collection on Pre-Post & 3 Months F/U Intervention Assessment Scales	7. Whether the blinding procedures were adequate?	Yes, we could adhere to double blinding, since the person who did allocation and sealed envelope was not involved in assessment and intervention in any way	The interventionist remained blinded to the group assignment till initiation of the intervention. The participants were totally blinded to their group allocation.	Successful
	8. Did participants adhere to the intervention?	Yes. Successful adherence to Interventions was defined as participants receiving at least 80% of the components of the intervention on each assigned day.	All 24 children in the intervention arms completed all tasks assigned on the scheduled days. 100% adherence	Successful
	9. Was the intervention acceptable to the participants?	Acceptability was measured by participant refusal to comply with therapy.	There was no exercise which participants refused to perform (100% agreement)	Successful. Acceptable.
	10. Was it possible to calculate intervention costs and duration?	Cost was not calculated in this feasibility trial	Duration of PSSCogRehab was increased to complete planned tasks/per session, while other two remained as planned after pre-testing	Cost was not calculated.
	11. Were outcome assessments completed?	Yes, all children were assessed at 3 time points, baseline, post-intervention, and 3 months follow up	100% completed outcome measures at T1, T2, and T3.	Successful. 3 months F/U assessment was done with mean days of gap of 101+-5days
Attrition (Excluding the dropout after baseline)	12. Were outcomes measured those that were the most appropriate outcomes?	All outcomes were deemed appropriate and valid as per literature	All assessments were repeated at 3 timepoints	Successful
	13. Was retention to the study good?	Successful retention was defined by less than 10% attrition rate for immediate Post intervention assessment and less than 20% for 3months F/U assessment.	Excellent Retention Rate: At T2 and T3= 100%. Not a single drop out or loss to follow up at T3.	Successful retention 0 Attrition
	14. Were the logistics of running a multi-centre trial assessed?	No, it was a single centre trial	The feasibility was assessed for single centre RCT	Not applicable
Adherence to Intervention: Completion of Sessions, and Tasks	15. Did all components of the intervention protocol work together?	Average no. of sessions and duration of each session estimated & actually conducted to work through the Intervention mostly remained same as in pre-test.	8 sessions each for 60-90mts duration was planned in the protocol and actually done, except PSSCog Rehab was increased beyond 90mts wherever required due the difficulty level of few tasks). Pretest of	Study processes were completed and met all pre-determined criteria at the end of the study. Session duration successfully increased by 30-60 minutes without any challenge

In Planned Intervention		Children completing 80% of planned tasks was considered as successful adherence.	interventions helped in adjustments in time taken per task and number of tasks per session.	as the parents were informed during the informed consent. Adherence to intervention was 100%.
	16. Was there any barrier to adherence?	Except Covid-19, no apparent barrier	Few children dropped out after randomization due to Parents' Covid infection	No barrier
Participant's Feedback on Intervention	17. Did the participants perceive the intervention interesting, capable to hold their attention and beneficial?	Participants' feedback were analysed.	Descriptive analysis of feedback of children. Children found few tasks very difficult (e.g. what I am doing, identify slow motion/walking, emotion recognition) in PSSCogRehab; and found few tasks less difficult (e.g. connect 4, for children aged 10-11 years in MCTT	Largely beneficial
Improvement due to Intervention	18. Did the interventions statistically improve cognitive functioning of the participants?	Improvement in cognitive functioning or reduction in cognitive deficits was defined as significant difference in scores from T-1 to T-3 with at least medium effect size of treatment effects.	MCTT and PSSCog Rehab had significant treatment effects with medium to large effect size	Medium to large effect size.
	19. Was the improvement solely due to interventions?	Possibly as they were asked not to be involved any other cognitive intervention before post 3 months assessment.	Extra activity sheets to practice at home were given, however, how many completed was not followed up.	Not successful in follow up of extra sheets on cognitive task for home work.
Other Criteria	20. Was there equipose of children and therapists?	It was presumed to be balanced	However, during intervention it was not consideration.	Not evaluated
	21. Did the feasibility study allow a sample size calculation for an RCT trial?	Yes. Inclusion criteria of ADHD aged 6-11 years without co-morbidity were maintained for a sample size calculation for an RCT trial	The sample size for the main study was calculated with 80% power estimation, which came to at least 45 in full RCT	Feasible trial successful. Main RCT study is possible.

Impact Analysis (Table-3)

Findings indicated there were significant difference on plan code (d=.66), plan connection (d=1.0), expressive attention (d=1.0), matrices (d=.82), visio-spatial relation(d=.61), word series(d=.54), and sentence repetition(d=.56), errors committed and time taken in Children's Colour Trails Test-1 (d=.59, d=1.0 respectively) and Test-2(d=.88) (d=1.0), and Porteus maze test (d=.97, d=.72 respectively) in the MCTT group. The significance level was p<.01 and effect size varied from medium to large on all measures.

Except on matrices, verbal spatial relations and word series in CAS-II and Porteus maze test errors committed, PSSCogRehab had significant positive effects similar to MCTT on plan code (d=.670), plan connection (d=1.0), expressive attention (d=.94), sentence repetition (d=.64),

times taken (d=1.0) and errors committed (d=.94) on Colour's Trial Test-1 and Test-2 (d=1.0, d=.72 respectively), and Porteus maze time taken (d=1.0).

On Cogmed, significant positive treatment effects were found on plan code (d=.47), plan connection (d=.67), word series (d=.44), sentence repetition (d=.77) in CAS-II, time taken and errors committed on colour's trail test-1(d=1.0 and d=.78 respectively) and test-2 (d=.94 and d=.93 respectively), and Porteus maze test time (d=.49).

The TAU group deteriorated significantly on Porteus maze test errors committed (d=.63) and time taken (d=.42), errors committed in Colour's Trail Test-1 (d=.97) and Test-2 (d=.93), time taken in colour's trail test-1(d=1.0), sentence repetition (d=.67), plan code (d=.52), and plan connection (d=.67).

Table 3: Comparison of Treatment Effects in Pre (T1), Post (T2), and Follow-Up (T3)

Cognitive Variables	Groups	Mean (SD) T1	Mean (SD) T2	Mean (SD) T3	χ ² Value T1, T2, T3	Significance level	Effect Size Cohen's d
Plan Code Total score	MCTT	55.62 (5.62)	73.62 (8.56)	80.50 (22.55)	10.51	.005	0.66 (M)
	PSS Cog	52.50 (12.15)	61.50 (11.18)	77.87 (24.29)	10.75	.005	0.67 (M)
	CogMed	51.62 (18.82)	58.12 (14.67)	65.62 (20.47)	7.54	.02	0.47(M)
	Control	50.25	43.00	38.75	8.26	.02	0.52

Plan Connection Total (in seconds)	MCTT	(13.38) 324.87 (241.5)	(13.54) 244.50 (144.7)	(6.11) 223.50 (137.66)	16.00	.00	1.0 (L)
	PSSCog	365.00 (118.03)	298.87 (108.12)	266.62 (94.15)	16.00	.00	1.0 (L)
	CogMed	289.87 (116.62)	255.87 (120.94)	261.25 (108.53)	10.75	.005	0.67(M)
	Control	384.12 (233.32)	388.00 (233.12)	388.87 (233.83)	10.75	.005	0.67 (M)
Expressive Attention	MCTT	36.37 (7.13)	32.00 (6.23)	30.00 (5.58)	16.00	.00	1.0 (L)
	PSS Cog	33.62 (11.14)	31.00 (10.11)	29.62 (9.28)	14.96	.001	.94 (L)
	CogMed	29.75 (14.22)	36.12 (7.33)	33.37 (5.34)	4.75	.09	0.297
	Control	32.62 (15.44)	25.00 (8.10)	21.12 (6.44)	2.00	.37	0.125
Matrices	MCTT	17.62 (3.96)	20.25 (5.70)	22.87 (4.82)	13.06	.001	0.82 (L)
	PSS Cog	16.62 (9.13)	19.75 (5.70)	21.62 (5.90)	4.71	.10	0.294
	CogMed	16.12 (5.08)	17.37 (4.62)	16.87 (5.08)	2.46	.29	0.154
	Control	17.12 (3.83)	14.87 (3.27)	12.37 (2.77)	5.44	.07	0.34
Verbal Spatial Relation	MCTT	13.87 (3.31)	16.75 (3.15)	19.12 (3.39)	9.80	.007	0.61 (M)
	PSS Cog	12.87 (6.28)	15.87 (5.61)	17.12 (5.76)	1.75	.42	0.11
	CogMed	13.25 (3.49)	16.00 (4.27)	16.87 (4.29)	5.09	.08	0.32
	Control	12.37 (3.77)	11.00 (4.07)	11.00 (2.77)	3.42	.18	0.21
Word Series	MCTT	13.87 (5.24)	17.37 (4.89)	18.75 (5.00)	8.58	.01	0.54 (M)
	PSS Cog	12.62 (6.04)	12.12 (4.45)	17.00 (3.20)	4.06	.13	0.25
	CogMed	11.25 (7.49)	11.50 (3.70)	15.12 (5.16)	7.03	.03	0.44 (M)
	Control	13.37 (3.15)	11.00 (3.16)	11.62 (3.06)	4.06	.13	0.25
Sentence Repetition	MCTT	8.50 (2.82)	11.50 (1.92)	13.50 (2.82)	9.00	.01	0.56 (M)
	PSS Cog	6.00 (3.74)	10.87 (4.45)	11.25 (3.53)	10.20	.006	0.64 (M)
	CogMed	6.50 (2.26)	10.75 (4.83)	9.75 (5.06)	12.28	.002	0.77 (M)
	Control	8.50 (2.82)	11.50 (1.92)	13.50 (2.82)	9.00	.01	0.67 (M)
Children's Color Trails Test-1 Time Taken	MCTT	65.37 (42.53)	46.37 (28.91)	32.12 (12.14)	16.00	.00	1.0 (L)
	PSS Cog	67.75 (56.29)	51.62 (56.71)	46.50 (57.20)	16.00	.00	1.0 (L)
	CogMed	67.75 (37.44)	53.87 (36.84)	44.00 (32.08)	16.00	.00	1.0 (L)
	Control	68.12 (43.85)	73.50 (44.38)	78.87 (43.46)	16.00	.00	1.0 (L)
Children's Color Trails Test-1 Error Committed	MCTT	3.37 (2.38)	0.25 (0.46)	0.12 (0.35)	9.50	.01	0.59(M)
	PSS Cog	3.37 (1.83)	1.50 (1.06)	0.62 (0.51)	14.96	.001	0.94 (L)
	CogMed	3.37	1.50	0.87	12.60	.002	0.78 (M)

4. Clarifies doubts of the child while the child is doing the activity	Clarifies doubts without answering the correct answer or jointly doing the activity for the child	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	100
5. Use of recording aids in sessions	Therapist uses stopwatch and recording sheets to record time, correct response, number of attempts, etc.	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	100
6. Helps the child to attain and maintain appropriate levels of alertness.	Explains new activities in an affective state (e.g. "Oh! Today's activity is very exciting or funny or interesting") that supports the child to actively engage in activities.	1.5	1.5	1.75	2.0	84.4
7. Encourages the child with positive feedback	Whenever the child does as per desired speed or accuracy or attempts and otherwise (e.g you have definitely improved from the previous session) also, the therapist gives positive feedback	1.75	2.0	1.75	2.0	93.75
8. Collaborates in activity choice	Collaborates in activity choice but as per the flexibility allowed in the manual	1.5	1.63	1.75	2.0	86
9. Ensures completion of all activities	Ensures that all activities in the designated difficulty level are completed	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	100
10. Takes feedback on child's experience	The therapist takes verbal and written feedback on child's overall experience on MCTT	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	100
Overall agreement on the consistency and reproducibility of MCTT						93.45%

Note: Adapted from Parham et. al., 2007. T- Therapist

Feedback Analysis

Majority (>87%) enjoyed on MCTT, 50% of children reported PSSCogRehab as difficult and 25% found it less enjoyable due to task repetition. 62.5% of children were not sure about continuing the sessions on CogMed despite the fact that more than 75% of children found the interventions benefitting their attention and concentration in some way.

DISCUSSION

Cognitive interventions can use a computer or pen-and-paper to train on focused cognitive tasks, with the goal of improving accuracy and speed (Velo, Vicente, and Filipe, 2020). Both formats emphasize adjusting to a child's existing ability (Diamond, 2012) and have the potential to lessen cognitive impairments that mediate pathophysiology to reduce symptoms (Cortese, et. al., 2015).

Feasibility Outcomes: Except cost and multi-centre trial potential, MCTT and PSSCogRehab were found to be feasible for children with ADHD aged 6-11 years. This could be due to factors such as, the sample enrollment rate was 3 per month and the recruitment timeline was wider for 38 randomized participants therefore, perhaps the staggered recruitment worked as a successful strategy (King, et. al., 2020). The higher conversion to consent rate, study enrollment and randomization, and 100% retention of participants after baseline assessment was consistent with previous literature (Denhoff, et. al., 2015). 100% adherence to and acceptability of interventions could be attributed to: 1) simple and straightforward information provision, flexible time slots of intervention as per children's conveniences, and consistent facilitation from the research team; 2) the nature of active intervention i.e. doing new activities either manually or in a computer which perhaps

kept the monotony and predictability of tasks intervention at bay, hence helped in sustained motivation; 3) the performance and feedback on various tasks perhaps provided a sense of competency to the children; and 4) participant's interest, engagement, involvement, and perceived benefits of the intervention. Especially, the total duration of MCTT and PSSCogRehab was 540 minutes (approximately) in 8 sessions over two weeks was intentionally designed to keep less burdensome as the motivation to seek treatment, adherence, and compliance were often fragile in children in developing countries (Burns, Cortell, & Wagner, 2008). Since CogMed had prior evidence and it was relatively shorter in duration compared to MCTT and PSSCogRehab, the feasibility issues were not anticipated. 100% retention in three groups might be due to children's perception of interventions as not too technical or demanding. It was better than clinic-based cognitive training programs with completion rates of approximately 70-80% (Skea, Newlands, & Gillies, 2019). Also, external factors, schools' closure due to Covid 2nd wave, perhaps it helped parents to bring the children anytime during the scheduled day of a session. Overall, therapists' rapport with the parents and children, clearly stated patient information sheet, eagerness of the parents to improve children's core cognitive deficits could have also contributed to the successful feasibility of the study. Moreover, specifying recruitment processes and creating an excel tracking sheet for each child (Denhoff, et al., 2015), telephonic reminders for sessions, allowing parents in the session and briefing them on child's performance, and updating the recruitment flow-chart every month to track progress could have facilitated the recruitment and retention outcomes. All components were adequately coagulated including random allocation, double blinding, delivering the interventions, outcome ascertainment, small sample size for feasibility,

ethical considerations, safety concerns, fidelity and feasibility analysis. The smooth amalgamation of all the constituents and well-ordered conduction of intervention might have helped.

Apart from 8 intervention sessions, children had 3 more sessions for baseline, immediate post, and 3-months follow up assessments. The average gap between date of baseline assessment and first session of intervention was 7 days, completion of intervention and immediate post-intervention assessment was 6 days, and completion of intervention and follow up assessment was 101 days (>3 months). The difficulty level of connect-4 activity in MCTT found to be easy for children aged 10-11 years. Similarly, difficulty level of tasks such as what I am doing, slow motion walk identify, and emotion recognition in PSSCogRehab can be modified to suit more to Indian. CogMed may be supplemented with variety of cognitive task as repetition of tasks induced boredom in children as experienced by children.

Impact Analysis:

MCTT had significantly reduced cognitive deficits with large effect size for plan connection, expressive attention, matrices, children's colour trail test-1 time taken, test-2 time taken and errors, porteus maze test time and error; and medium effect size for plan code, verbal-spatial relation, word series, sentence repetition, and children's colour trail test-1 errors. Children with ADHD display a diverse set of neurocognitive deficits and since MCTT contained cognitive tasks in 9 domains with 8 increasing difficulty levels and 36 activities, it benefitted as a more effective strategy compared to a single domain. The study on comparison of a non-computerized school-based training "paying attention in class" to CogMed working memory computerized training (van der Donk, et al., 2015) was partially similar to our study. Our study was different from studies found treatment effects of CogMed on other academic tasks (Egeland, Aarlien, & Saunes, 2013). However, the non-computerized training in van der Donk et al.'s study (van der Donk, et al., 2015) focused on attention, working memory and planning skills through psychoeducation on executive function; three paper and pencil adaptive WM tasks namely, visual spatial span task, a listening recall span task, and an instruction paradigm task (30 trials in total) practiced daily to improve WM capacity; and performing school related tasks with audiobook cues. Our study was different in terms of 1) nature of intervention and its replicability potential; 2) sample profile as ADHD children with comorbid learning disabilities (LDs) and/or oppositional defiant disorder (ODD) constituted the sample in Pay Attention study whereas we recruited children without any co-morbid condition; (Egeland, Aarlien, & Saunes, 2013) we had younger children aged 6-11 years as compared to 8-12 years; 4) we had one TAU (with 1 psychoeducation session to parents) considered as a control

group whereas there was none in Pay Attention study (van der Donk, et al., 2015) and no-contact TAU as controls in Egeland, et al.'s study (Egeland, Aarlien, & Saunes, 2013); teachers were partially engaged in one part of Pay Attention intervention as against MCTT, CogMed, PSSCogRehab which are entirely child-focused interventions; and the standard Cogmed protocol followed in Pay Attention training (5 weeks, five times a week, ~45 min a day vs 8 days over two weeks with 90min a day in our study).

Children remained engaged, motivated to practice during MCTT and PSSCogRehab as compared to Cogmed due to repetitiveness of tasks in Cogmed (feedback). MCTT had better options in adjusting difficulty level and choice of tasks to match with the performance and interest of the child (Cortese, et al., 2015) compared to computerized tools, therefore perhaps changes occurred in all measuring tools sustained even after 3 months.

The significant positive effects of PSSCogRehab on planning, expressive attention, working memory, and other attention tasks were in line with its impact studied in normal children in middle school (Hovik, et al., 2013). Cogmed primarily worked on planning and working memory and the findings were similar to earlier studies on children with AHDD (van der Donk, et al., 2015, Egeland, Aarlien, and Saunes, 2013). Though the preliminary evidence on the treatment effects indicated the significant positive benefits (with medium-large effect size) of MCTT over both computerized tools, and findings indicated benefits of all three interventions over TAU. The positive effects were also sustained on majority of tools till 3 months post-intervention. However, MCTT does not claim the effects emphatically primarily due to small sample size. Although the purpose of this study was not to compare the efficacy, and size of variability of difference between interventions, (Abbott, 2014; Orsmond & Cohn, 2015; Parham, 2011; Shanyinde, et al., 2011; Stewart, 2020) we attempted primarily to understand the feasibility and comparability of manualized and computerized cognitive intervention in a prospective full-size RCT study. Further, our intention of impact assessment was similar to studies suggesting unavailability of data from previous studies to indicate the likely baseline status and no evidence informing the minimal important clinical difference (MICD) of MCTT and PSSCogRehab on performance based neuropsychological measures, therefore such data was required for sample size calculation for a full-size RCT (Noordzij, et al., 2010).

Fidelity Analysis of MCCT

The finding of more than 90% agreement on the procedural element's adherence by both the raters in MCTT established its fidelity. A theoretically-based, process-oriented, structured and procedure-focused manual with well-described cognitive tasks in the MCTT manual perhaps resulted in enhanced fidelity and

replicability potentiality. Also, a structured fidelity instrument contributed to establish its treatment integrity and helped the raters to verify the intervention delivery methods described in the manual. Structural elements of fidelity analysis of MCTT were not analyzed as it was delivered in a fixed therapy room (which was spacious, noise free, and air-conditioned) for all, and length of each cognitive task, duration of all sessions, etc. were pre-defined as in the MCTT manual (Cortese, et. al., 2015).

Feedback analysis

Children in the intervention groups found the cognitive task very engaging, beneficial, and enjoyable and parents found the interventions improving child's attention, other cognitive functioning, along with academic performance.

CONCLUSION

MCTT met majority of feasibility and fidelity criteria thus, ready for a full-size randomized controlled clinical trial as per the Medical Research Council guidelines (Craig, et. al., 2008). The far transfer effects on other non-training cognitive tasks could be explored. Although all MCTT, Cogmed and PSSCogRehab had comparable positive effects, PSSCogRehab needs cultural adaptation for Indian children with ADHD.

Ethics: The Institute Ethics Committee of a large public sector tertiary care teaching hospital approved the study (IEC/624/10/2017 during the development of MCTT and IEC-349/06.07.2018, RP-37/2018 for this study).

Patients' Consent: Informed written consent in Hindi/English was taken from the parents/legal guardians and assent from children as per IEC norms.

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